

International Rice Genetic Survey. Copies of the lists were sent to the senior rice breeder of each research center, with the request that he provide each variety's cross, and add new varieties not recorded and the year of release.

We then plotted the percentages of new varieties that were progeny of major gene sources released from 1965 to 1970, from 1971 to 1975, and from 1976 to 1980.

The most heavily used semidwarf parents in crosses were Taichung Native 1 (TN1) and IR8. The other semidwarf parents were categorized as *locally developed* (bred by the national

programs); *other IRRI* (any IRRI cultivar other than IR 8); and *introduced from another country* (for example if Sona, an Indian semidwarf, were used in Indonesian crosses).

TN1 was used in 22% of all the crosses analyzed for 1965-67, and appeared as a parent of 40% of the new varieties released in the same nations by 1970 (see figure). The steady decline in its use as a parent in the subsequent decade was matched by a corresponding decline in its appearance as a direct parent of new varieties released.

IR8 was involved in about 20% of the crosses made in the mid-1960s and was

a parent of about 25% of the varieties released 5 or 6 years later. Its use in crosses increased and then declined; so did its subsequent appearance as a parent of varieties. Breeders had almost stopped using IR8 as a parent by 1975, but it was a parent of 24% of the varieties released from that time until 1980.

The strongest trend found in the 1975 survey was the increasing use of locally developed semidwarfs as parents—from 0 to about 50% from 1965 to 1975. But of the subsequent varieties, only about 20% are progeny of those crosses. Most of the local semidwarf parents were progeny of IR8 or TN1. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Sheath rot incidence and chaffy grain percentage on some popular rices

V.S. Thri Murty, O. P. Veda, R. G. Satputhe, and R. Kashyap, J.N.K.V.V. Research Farm, Sarkanda, Bilaspur, Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

The incidence of sheath rot of rice and percentage of resulting chaffiness on some popular varieties grown in the Chhattisgarh region of MP in 1979

kharif were recorded. Nine varieties were grown in a replicated trial with fertilizer applied at 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha with 3 replications/variety.

The disease incidence was assessed by observing for sheath rot symptoms 10 plants from 3 patches selected for each replication. The percentage of infection was calculated by counting the infected and healthy panicles for each plant (see table).

The infected panicles that showed sheath rot symptoms were randomly collected from the plots and pooled. Because neck rot infection also increases chaffy grain production, care was taken to select neck rot-free panicles. The chaffy and filled grains of 10 panicles were counted. The healthy panicles with no sheath rot or neck rot served as control. The percentage of chaffy grains was higher in the diseased panicles than in the healthy ones.

Percentage of sheath rot incidence and chaffy grains developed. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Panicle infection (%)	Chaffy grains (%) on	
		Diseased panicles	Healthy panicles
Phakuna	28.8	31.0	8.2
Madhuri	31.2	49.5	9.4
Anupama	32.0	45.8	8.9
Jaya	37.2	32.6	7.5
Kranti	38.0	37.5	11.5
Patel 85	49.5	38.0	12.0
Pragati	53.2	42.0	10.5
Bangoli 5	62.7	30.1	11.0
Patel 17	72.5	48.0	15.0

Patel 17 had maximum incidence and Phalguna minimum. Bangoli 5 had more infection than Phalguna, but the latter had a higher percentage of chaffiness.

Similar observations were made on Patel 17 and Anupama. This indicates that the time of panicle infection may play an important role in chaffy grain production. ■

Outbreak of sheath rot on rice

K. Muralidharan and G. Venkata Rao, Regional Rice Research Station, Nellore 524003 India

During late kharif 1978-79, an outbreak of sheath rot (caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) occurred at Nellore. In October, entries in the national screening nursery were planted singly in 2 rows, each 3 m long. A spacing of 20 x 15 cm was adopted. Urea at 150 kg N/ha was applied in 3 equal splits. Sheath rot was observed at the panicle initiation stage. Unusual rains in December (153 mm), in addition to cool moist weather with

relative humidity of 95% and above on many days, helped spread the disease.

The rot appeared on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Oblong lesions on the leaf sheath coalesced quickly and covered most of the sheath. Among 673 entries tested, 124 recorded clear susceptible reactions (score 5-9). In these susceptible entries almost every panicle was damaged by the fungus. Panicles either remained within the leaf sheath or emerged only partially. Young panicles rotted completely. Profuse powdery growth of the fungus was found inside affected leaf sheaths.